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A Framework to create a Laboratory Twin from *in situ* Tidal Energy Site Measurements

Christopher Ruhl, Mohd Hanzla, Arindam Banerjee¹

Mechanical Engineering & Mechanics, Lehigh University, 19 Memorial Drive W., Bethlehem, PA 18015, United States

Abstract

Turbulent flow conditions at in-situ tidal energy deployment locations can directly impact parameters such as available energy extraction, fatigue life of turbine blades, and the development of the downstream turbine wake. A Tidal Turbulence Testing Facility has been developed, in part, to recreate site-specific turbulent characteristics in its open surface, recirculating water tunnel using an active grid turbulence generator. This first-of-its-kind active grid turbulence generator is designed for use in water. The current study explores the ability to develop grid operating procedures to mimic turbulent flow conditions from a specific highly energetic tidal site in the Turbulence Testing Facility water tunnel. Data from a previous *in situ* measurement campaign using acoustic Doppler velocimeters allowed for the calculation of mean flow velocity, turbulence intensity, integral length scales, and turbulence spectra relevant for tidal site characterization and valuable for turbine designers and developers. The ability to reproduce these precise statistics in a laboratory setting is then explored using the capabilities of the active grid. In particular, we discuss our efforts on twinning one tidal energy site to demonstrate the framework that can be applied to other sites.

Keywords: active grid; laboratory twin; turbulence; tidal energy

1. Introduction

Inflow turbulence and anisotropy in the freestream are rarely accounted for during the design and lower TRL (<6) testing phase of a tidal energy convertor. Turbulence at a tidal site is highly anisotropic, a feature that is not replicated (or controlled) in experiments and computations. To date, there have been several efforts in Europe, especially at the wave and current flume tank, where higher turbulence intensity inflow was attained by adding (static) turbulence generation techniques or removing the flow conditioning screens upstream of the test section [1-3]. These studies are limited since inflow turbulence is not tunable as they use passive turbulence generators and cannot mimic features (anisotropy, length scale, spectrum) of high-energy tidal sites. Computational efforts that can mimic tidal flows and estimate hydrodynamic loads on turbines are limited to high-fidelity models like Large Eddy Simulations [4, 5] and are expensive from the developer's point of view, as design iterations using those methods incur huge computational costs. In this study, we explore the benchmarking of the Tidal Turbulence Test Facility (T³F) at Lehigh University to *twin* the inflow flood and ebb tide conditions at Nodule Point (Puget Sound, WA). Development and benchmarking of the T³F will allow early-stage developers (TRL: 1-5) to perform design iterations and structural health monitoring in a framework of tidal site-specific turbulence. Using these data sets, developers can identify failure

¹ Corresponding author. Co-Director, Atlantic Marine Energy Center, Lehigh University, Bethlehem, PA 18015 USA.
E-mail: arb612@lehigh.edu

modes and perform design iterations at lower TRL (≤ 5) levels. This would make the design more robust and provide additional confidence before open water testing (TRL >6). The turbulence inflow datasets can also be used for developing synthetic turbulence protocols that can be included as representative tidal turbulence spectrum [6].

2. Methods

2.1. Lehigh University Tidal Turbulence Testing Facility

The Tidal Turbulence Testing Facility, located at Lehigh University (Bethlehem, PA) is home to a recirculating water flume with an open surface test section measuring 0.61m wide \times 0.61m tall \times 1.98m long. Flow is driven by a 25HP single-stage axial flow propeller pump. In the current configuration, the tunnel is capable of reaching flow speeds up to 1.0 m/s with a pending pump upgrade that will increase the flow speed in the test section to 1.9-2.0 m/s. The facility is equipped with a Makita-type active grid turbulence generator, meaning there is an array of flow-agitating winglets connected to rotating shafts that are each controlled by a dedicated stepper motor. The control parameters of the water channel and active grid are listed in Table 1. The produced turbulent flow from this study was measured by a laboratory ADV to gather point-wise measurements in the centerline of the tunnel. Previous work by our group [7, 8] has demonstrated that the active grid can be used to tailor desired individual flow characteristics that include turbulence intensity, integral length scales, and turbulence spectra within range, by strategically altering the angular velocity of the winglets, the blockage ratio of the winglets, and the freestream velocity.

Table 1. Overview of the water tunnel and active grid parameters varied to determine the capabilities of turbulent flow produce in the T³F.

Varied Parameter	Dimensionless Parameter	Options/Values Tested
Operating Protocols	-	Synchronous, Single Random, Double Random
Winglet Blockage Ratio	-	25.3%, 27.3%, 40.2%, 59.2%, 74.0%
Inflow Velocity, U_∞	$Re_M = U_\infty M / \nu$	0.10m/s, 0.20m/s, 0.40m/s, 0.60m/s, 0.83m/s
Shaft Angular Velocity, Ω	$Ro = U_\infty / M\Omega$	0.10Hz, 0.25Hz, 1.00Hz, 3.00Hz
Downstream Distance, X	X/M	2.5, 5.0, 10.0, 15.0, 17.5

M is the mesh length of the active grid, which measures the distance between the center points of each winglet. In this study, $M = 0.102$ m. Synchronous uses a constant Ω for a continuous period of rotation; Single Random uses a constant Ω and randomizes the period rotation; Double Random randomizes both Ω and the period of rotation

2.2. Tidal Energy Site Measurements

The *in situ* measurements used in this study were obtained from an open-source database [9] that contains the data sets for the measurement campaign at Nodule Point in Puget Sound (WA, USA). More detailed information on the measurement instrumentation and procedures can be found in Thomas *et al.* [10]. Relevant parameters of the ADV measurement campaign can be found in Table 2. The dataset contains 4 days of measurements, which encompasses multiple ebb and flood cycles.

Table 2. Basic parameters of the Nodule Point tidal site (Puget Sound, WA) measurement campaign

Lat / Lon	Duration	Water Depth [m]	ADV Height [m]	Sampling Freq. [Hz]
N 48.01924' / W 122.39689'	2/17/11 – 2/21/11	22	4.7	32

2.3. Post Processing the ADV datasets

The raw laboratory and *in situ* ADV datasets were processed using an algorithm (developed in MATLAB) that uses a phase space thresholding (PST) technique described in Goring and Nikora [11] to eliminate spikes and replace outliers in the data. Our custom-built code allows the user to select an appropriate window averaging time (WAT) to parse data into time-based statistical groupings. This is necessary for tidal site data as conditions are not stagnant. A proper WAT requires a period long enough that statistics have converged, but not too long where the statistics drift as the inherent nature of the flow substantially changes. A statistical convergence analysis confirms a 5-minute WAT is acceptable for the data used in the current study from Nodule Point.

2.4. Characterizing the Turbulent Flow

Turbulence is chaotic in nature. A series of statistical parameters were selected to characterize the laboratory-based and tidal site turbulence and to facilitate the comparison between the flows. These parameters, which are commonly used in site characterization studies [10, 12] include mean velocity (U), turbulence intensity (I_U), integral length scales (L_U), and energy spectra, typically in the streamwise direction. The statistical analysis begins with instantaneous velocities collected by the ADV in the streamwise, cross-stream, and vertical directions, denoted as $u(t)$, $v(t)$, and $w(t)$ respectively. From here, Reynolds decomposition can be imposed (shown below for the streamwise direction) as follows,

$$u(t) = U + u'(t) \quad (1)$$

where U is the time-averaged velocity and $u'(t)$ is the time-dependent fluctuating component. The decomposition allows for the calculation of turbulence intensity, I_u , defined as,

$$I_u = \frac{u'_{rms}}{U} \quad (2)$$

where the *rms* subscript indicates the root-mean-square function.

The integral length scales, L_u , represent the large energy-containing eddies in the flow and are estimated from the integral time scale, τ_u , calculated by,

$$\tau_u = \int_0^{s_0} \rho_u(s) ds; \text{ and } \rho_u(s) \equiv \frac{\langle u(t)u(t+s) \rangle}{\langle u(t)^2 \rangle} \quad (3)$$

where ρ is the autocorrelation function, s is the time lag, s_0 is a time where the autocorrelation function is sufficiently low, and $\langle \rangle$ indicates a time averaging operator. From here, Taylor's frozen turbulence hypothesis [13] can be applied to find the integral length scale $L_u = U\tau_u$.

Energy spectra in turbulent flow can reveal information regarding the transfer of energy through different scales in the flow, indicated by what is known as the energy cascade. The energy spectra in this study were determined using the *pwelch* function in MATLAB utilizing 5-minute time series divided into eight segments using a window function (Hamming) with 50% overlap.

3. Mimicking Laboratory-generated Turbulence and *In Situ* Tidal Site Measurements.

3.1. Mean Flow Speed

Tidal flow speeds in nature are governed by the relative distance between the sun, moon, and Earth. At a local scale, the shape of the tidal estuary and bathymetry of the site influences mean flow speed. This is the case with the Nodule Point site. Conversely, free stream velocity in the T³F laboratory water tunnel is controlled by the input settings of a propeller pump. Mean speeds in the test section are then further influenced by the active grid. The mean flows

Figure 1. A 27 hour excerpt of mean velocities measured at Nodule Point (blue) and the mean velocity capabilities of the T³F before upgrade (red line and gray region). (a) a timeseries of the data, revealing the T³F can achieve ~50% of the maximum velocity at Nodule Point. (b) a histogram which reveals the current T³F capabilities (i.e. prior to upgrade) are sufficient for ~40% of the measured velocities.

Figure 2. (a) Comparison of the turbulence intensity values measured at Nodule Point (blue) and produced using the active grid in the T³F (red). (b, c) Assessment of the integral length scales measured at Nodule Point (blue) and produced using the active grid in the T³F (red) using both (b) raw measures and (c) measures non-dimensionalized by channel depth.

from a 27-hour segment of the Nodule Point measurement campaign and the maximum mean flow from the T³F parametric study are shown in Figure 1. The grey region indicates the (current) capable mean velocities using the T³F which can be achieved by altering the water channel pump frequency, with the maximum velocity determined to be $U_{max} = 0.919$ m/s. Figure 1 shows while the T³F can mimic lower flow speeds from Nodule Point, it falls short of replicating peak velocities, particularly in flood tides, where the most significant forcings are expected to occur. An upgrade to the T³F pump is scheduled for later in the Fall of 2023 to match mean flow speeds.

3.2. Turbulence Intensity

The range of turbulence intensity in the T³F was determined by varying the control parameters of the active grid. The results of the active grid turbulence coupled with the mean velocity are plotted with likewise measurements from Nodule Point in Figure 2a. Note, results where $U < 0.5$ m/s were omitted as turbulence intensity becomes excessive at meaning at such low velocities and carries little meaning. These velocities represent slack conditions which are often excluded when reporting turbulence statistics in a site characterization study [10]. Figure 2a shows the active grid is capable of replicating turbulence intensity values found at Nodule Point at flow velocities of $U = 0.6$ and 0.83 m/s. The maximum turbulence intensity achieved by the T³F active grid at $U = 0.6$ and 0.83 m/s were $I_u = 18.7\%$ and 17.7% , respectively. Both of these values are well within the maximum turbulence intensity measured at Nodule Point, excluding three samples that verge on statistical outlier classification. The variance of turbulence intensity at Nodule Point lessens significantly as the velocity increases ($\sigma_{U < 1.0 \text{ m/s}} = 2.11$ to $\sigma_{U > 1.0 \text{ m/s}} = 1.22$, where σ indicates standard deviation). This means if the velocity capabilities of the T³F are enhanced, a lesser range of turbulence intensity values is required to match the Nodule Point flow conditions.

3.3. Integral Length Scale

In order to determine the spatial structures of turbulence, the integral length scales are analyzed. These scales represent the large, energy-containing eddies in the flow. The range of integral length scales measured at Nodule Point and produced in the T³F is shown in Figure 2b. The streamwise scales are plotted as these scales are typically much greater in magnitude than cross-stream and vertical length scales [12]. As expected, the absolute measures of streamwise integral length scales at Nodule Point are significantly larger (i.e. in some cases 100 times larger) than the length scales produced in the T³F, which is an artifact of the bathymetry and other site-specific and size-dependent features. To assist in the analysis, the integral length scales are non-dimensionalized using the tidal site or laboratory channel depth, h , for both Nodule Point ($h = 22$ m) and the T³F flume ($h = 0.61$ m) In this particular exercise, the T³F produces comparable length scales when normalized by channel depth with that of Nodule Point at the measured velocities.

3.4. Energy Spectra

The energy spectra for flow from Nodule Point and the T³F are represented in Figure 3. The spectrum from a particular T³F test case (Double Random protocol, $\Omega = 1.00$ Hz, $U = 0.80$ m/s, Blockage Ratio = 40.2%, $X/M = 5.0$) is shown in red in each figure. Each spectrum is comprised of data collected at 32 Hz. Figure 3a shows all energy spectra samples from Nodule Point, dividing the datasets into 5-minute windows and classifying each by the mean

Figure 3. Streamwise energy spectrum for one selected case from the T³F having $U = 0.80$ m/s and from Nodule Point (a) all energy spectra categorized by velocity (see colorscale); (b) energy spectrum from a tide of similar velocity to the sample from the T³F. Fine lines represent individual spectra of 5min windows using 8 subwindows and 50% overlap.

velocity using the gray color scale. Figure 3b shows a sample taken from Nodule Point with a comparable velocity to the sample used from the T³F. Each spectrum is made up of three regions: a low-frequency region indicative of the largest energy-containing eddies in the flow; a mid-frequency region marked by a $-5/3$ slope, characteristic of the inertial subrange which is the region where eddy size and energy content diminish to lesser and lesser values in a cascading fashion [13]; and a high-frequency range which theoretically indicates when the energy from the turbulent eddies are dissipated to heat, though in many cases instrumentation sampling rate is insufficient to resolve eddies so minuscule and thus the high-frequency region is dominated by instrument noise. The limitations of the ADVs restrict meaningful comparisons to be made at high wavenumber (small scale) values; however, for large scales, Figure 3b, shows for a sample of comparable mean velocity, the size and energy content of the large scales are significantly larger than that from the T³F, which is corroborated from the integral length scale analysis. Also of note, the Nodule Point data enters its energy cascade at a lower frequency (larger scales) than the laboratory-created turbulence. The T³F spectrum shows similar energy content for a larger range of wavenumbers.

4. Discussion and Future Work

Uncovering the ability of the T³F to replicate turbulent flow conditions measured at Nodule Point was met with preliminary success. The capabilities to reproduce turbulence statistics from Nodule Point are summarized with cumulative distribution functions (CDFs) for mean velocity, turbulence intensity, and normalized integral length scales in Figure 4. The plots show both the 95th percentile and the maximum range of the produced parameters from the T³F. The T³F is currently capable of matching around 50% of the magnitude of the maximum flow speed of Nodule Point. The capable range, however, encompasses the 40% of the samples collected, meaning velocity is met 40% of the time. The T³F is scheduled to upgrade the axial pump to reach flow speeds of up to $U = 1.9 - 2.0$ m/s, which will fully contain the range of flows found at Nodule Point and various other tidal energy sites. Turbulence intensity and channel-depth normalized integral length scales are well-matched at the mean velocities tested, which can be attributed to the unique active grid technology in the T³F. Nearly the entire span ($> 99\%$) of the measured turbulence intensity values at Nodule Point were reproduced in the T³F by fine-tuning the active grid parameters to match the flow, while 94% of the measured non-dimensionalized length scales are encompassed by the 95th percentile capability from the T³F study. Further work is planned to characterize the facility at peak tides following the water tunnel velocity upgrade.

Figure 4. Cumulative distribution functions (blue) displaying (a) mean velocity, (b) turbulence intensity, and (c) non-dimensionalized integral length scales measured at Nodule Point in this study. The dashed red lines and gray regions indicate the values within the CDF that can be replicated by the T³F. Percentages are labeled for a clear visual representation of the proportion of data able to be mimicked by the T³F.

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